

A Comparative Study of CSR in Public and Private Banking Sector

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19425594>

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Abstract:

In India CSR is mandatory for all the companies including banking companies. In India banks are generally divided into public sector banks and private sector banks. Public sector banks are registered under the banking companies act and act passing in parliament while private banks are registered under the companies act 2013. Since there is minor difference between public sector banks and private sector banks, it becomes crucial to study the CSR spending patterns of the public sector banks and private sector banks. The companies act 2013 makes all the companies to spent two percent of the profit on CSR. Here interesting to know that whether all the banks including public and private are making statutory compliance of the companies act 2013 or not. Since the act clearly state to spent two percent of profit on CSR, it becomes equally important to know the relationship between profitability and CSR. Ultimately, it is the profit which will be spent on the CSR. To study the statutory compliance of CSR, relationship between profitability and CSR and CSR expenditure pattern of the public sector banks and private sector banks, the researcher has selected the above topic.

Keywords: *Corporate Social Responsibility, Public Sector Banks, Private Sector Banks, The Companies Act 2013.*

Introduction:

India is the first country in the world who has made CSR mandatory. The government of India amended the Companies Act 1956 and renamed it the Companies Act 2013. The new act had many new features. One of the new features among the act was the section 135. The section 135 of the Companies Act 2013 makes CSR mandatory for the all the companies registered under this act or previous act. This makes all the companies mandatory to spent CSR including banking companies. This act makes all the banking companies registered under this act compulsory to spent two percent of average last three years profit to spend on CSR. Although this is the case, public banks are registered under the banking companies act 1949 or after passing special act in a parliament. Therefore, public sector banks find an excuse stating that they have not registered under the

companies act 2013 or previous act and hence spending two percent of average last three years profit on CSR is not mandatory to them. Therefore, they are spending voluntary one percent of profit on CSR. It means public sector banks are doing CSR activities voluntarily while private sector banks are doing CSR compulsorily. Therefore, it is important to do comparative study of CSR activities of public sector banks and private sector banks.

Literature Review:

1. Namrata Singh, Dr. Rajlaxmi Srivastava, and Dr. Rajni Rastogi (2015), in their study titled “An Analysis of CSR Spending in Banking Sector in India,” evaluated CSR expenditure patterns of 19 Indian banks. In their study they have stated that both public sector banks and private sector banks need to enhance their CSR spending. Comparatively, private banks have spent more than public sector banks. Private banks found being more strategic and long-term approach while public sector banks have focused on donations, sponsorships and relief funds.
2. Dr. Vishwas K. Shah (2021) states that public sector banks are spending their CSR funds on financial inclusion, rural development, education, and priority sector while private banks are focusing on digital literacy, environment sustainability and skill development program. The private banks are spending more than the public sector banks.
3. Payal Shastri (2022) states that private sector banks are more conscious towards CSR spendings and reporting practices while public sector banks are not accurate in their CSR spendings and reporting practices. In the annual reports of the private banks, they have reported required information in pursuance of CSR law while public sector banks have not reported CSR information as expected in pursuance of CSR law.
4. Dr. B. Shailaja (2022) in her research paper states that introduction of section 135 has influenced CSR expenditure significantly. It has been observed that banks are taking structured initiatives in spending CSR which are in aligned with national development. The priority sectors are education, healthcare, rural development and environment sustainability. Although this is the case, there is a difference between public sector banks and private sector banks spendings specifically in governance ad strategic focus. It has been found that the both the sector banks need structured monitoring, impact assessment, and transparent disclosure mechanism to enhance effectiveness of CSR program.

Statement of the problem:

1. Under the Companies Act 2013 CSR has become mandatory, still there is a significant variation in the approach, allocation of funds and implementation of CSR activities between public and private sector banks.
2. There is a lack of comparison of statutory compliance of CSR, relationship of profitability and CSR spendings and CSR expenditure pattern.

Objectives of the study:

1. To compare the statutory compliance of Section 135 of the Companies Act, 2013 among public and private sector banks.
2. To evaluate the relationship between profitability and CSR spending in public and private sector banks.
3. To analyse and compare CSR expenditure percentage of CSR of public and private sector banks over a specified period.

Justification of the objectives:

Although the CSR has become mandatory under the Companies Act 2013, there is significant difference in spending of the CSR between public and private sector banks. Hence it is important to study that whether all the public sector banks and private sector banks make statutory compliance. Since CSR is spending from the profit, therefore, becomes important to know the relationship between profitability and CSR spendings.

Need of the study:

India has introduced section 135 in Companies Act 2013 which makes CSR mandatory for eligible companies. Banking companies are being major entities in India, plays a significant role in fulfilling statutory requirement of CSR. A structured study of CSR spending of the banking companies is needed to be studied to examine the statutory compliance of CSR, relationship of profitability and CSR and CSR expenditure pattern.

Relevance & Importance of the study:

This study will provide comparative analysis of statutory compliance of CSR of public banks and private banks. It will help us to understand the relationship between profitability and CSR of public sector banks and private sector banks. The research will also make us understand the CSR expenditure pattern of public sector banks and private sector banks.

Working Definitions of terms used:

The following will be working definitions used in this research paper.

1. **Corporate Social Responsibility:** It is an ethical and moral responsibility of the business organization to contribute towards the society where they operate their businesses. In India, it has made compulsory to spend two percent of profit on CSR activities under the companies act 2013 to the eligible companies. It is expected to enhance and improve the lives of the employees, local communities and society at large through CSR activities.
2. **Banking Companies:** Banking companies are the financial institutions which are engaged in primary banking functions i.e. accepting deposits and lending loans. Companies which functions banking operations are called as banking companies. These companies are registered under the Companies Act 2013 and Banking Companies Act 1949 or after passing special act in parliament.
3. **Public Banks and Private Banks:** Public sector banks are the banks where majority of the shareholding (more than 50%) is own by the central or state government. These banks primarily work to achieve socio-economic objectives, financial inclusion and implement government policies. On the other hand, private banks are the banks where majority shareholding is own by the private individuals, corporate bodies or other institutions. These banks work with profit motives emphasising on innovations, competitiveness and customer centric services.

Research Methodology:

The present research is based on secondary data. The data is collected from annual reports of the banks, CSR portal of Indian government and other sources like websites, magazines, newspaper, books, research journals etc.

Population and Sample Selection:

As per the report of the RBI of FY 2021-22, in India there are twelve (12) public sector banks and twenty-two (22) private sector banks. The present study has included four public sector banks and five private sector banks in India. The banks are selected using the stratified sampling method. The parameter for the sample selection was the deposits of the banks of the FY 2021-22. The public banks selected for the study are Bank of Maharashtra, Bank of India, Union Bank of India and State Bank of India. The private sector banks selected for the study are HDFC Bank, ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, IDBI Bank and IndusInd Bank.

Justification of sampling method & sampling procedure:

The purpose behind the use of the stratified sample method was to select the banks which can represent the whole banking sector and not only the best performer among the bank. When the banks which represent the whole banking sector is selected, then it can give us actual situation of the banking sector. Therefore, stratified sampling method is selected to select the sample size for this study.

Scope of the study:

The present study will include four public sector banks and five private sector banks in India. The study is for the period of ten years from FY 2014-15 to FY 2023-24. The study is based on secondary data collected from the annual reports of banks and CSR portal of the government.

Limitations of the Study:

This study is based on the secondary data. The present study has studied the annual reports of the banks and CSR portal of Indian government. Based on this data the study is conducted.

Sources and methods of data collection:

The present research is based on the secondary data which is collected from the annual reports of the banks and CSR portal of Indian government.

Tools Techniques of Data Analysis:

MS-Excel is used to analyze the data. Tables and graphs are used in data analysis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:**Actual CSR spent by the banks in Percentage**

Financial Year	BOM	BOI	UBI	SBI	HDFC	ICICI	Axis Bank	IDBI	IndusInd
2011-12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2012-13	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2013-14	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2014-15	0.31	0.44	0.70	0.95	1.75	1.90	2.36	1.40	1.61
2015-16	0.15	0.60	0.37	1.13	2.30	1.76	2.20	0.73	1.92
2016-17	0.09	-1.17	0.45	0.97	2.95	1.78	1.86	-0.78	1.85
2017-18	0.00	-0.11	0.45	1.01	3.03	1.66	2.08	-0.05	0.88
2018-19	0.00	-0.09	-0.04	0.36	3.00	1.05	3.39	0.00	1.90
2019-20	-0.01	-0.13	-0.02	1.72	3.02	2.02	3.51	0.00	3.32
2020-21	-0.08	-0.12	-0.02	4.94	2.94	3.33	4.15	0.00	2.51
2021-22	-0.06	0.00	-0.55	1.71	2.81	2.91	3.21	0.00	3.06

2022-23	1.65	0.00	1.34	1.43	2.61	2.93	2.85	-0.05	2.65
2023-24	0.00	0.22	0.63	1.47	2.53	2.18	1.94	1.58	2.62

Source: Annual Report of the above mentioned banks.

Public Sector Bank Analysis:

The above table and graph show the CSR spending of the four public sector banks and five private sector banks. The public sector banks are Bank of Maharashtra, Bank of India, Union Bank of India and State Bank of India. The private sector banks are HDFC Bank, ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, IDBI and IndusInd Bank. The study is conducted for the period of ten years from FY 2014-15 to FY 2023-24. The above graph indicates year wise CSR spendings of the selected banks. The percentage of the CSR spends by the public banks and private banks are given. The colourful graphs indicate the banks name. On the x axes name of banks are given while on the y axes percentage is given. Banks are identified with different colours of the bars.

The actual CSR spending in percentage of Bank of Maharashtra during these periods are below the minimum requirement of CSR spending. It means Bank of Maharashtra has not made statutory compliance of spending two percent of profit on CSR. The graph is also clearly indicating the Bank of Maharashtra has spent less than the actual requirement. The table shows that Bank of India has

spent below the minimum requirement of the CSR spending in first two years while from third year onwards bank has spent more than the minimum requirement and in the last two years bank has spent below the minimum requirement. Not in a single year bank of India has spent more than one percentage of its profit on CSR activities. The above table indicates that UBI has not spent two percent of profit on CSR in any year. It means statutory compliance was not followed by the bank. The percentage wise UBI has spent more than one percent in two years only. Other eight years bank has spent below the one percent of average profit on CSR. It means UBI has not even spent one percentage of its profit on CSR activities. The data shows that SBI has spent more than one percentage of profit on CSR in most of the years. But the bank could not touch the two-percentage mark which is mandatory by the companies' act 2013. In the FY 2020-21 SBI has spent more than four percent. The rest of the year's bank has not complied with the companies' act 2013.

The above four public sector bank's analysis shows that they have not spent two percentage of their profit on CSR. Almost all the years all public sector banks have not made statutory compliance of the CSR. Only SBI has spent more than two percent on one financial year. It has been found that there is direct of relations of profitability of bank and CSR spending.

Private Sector Banks Analysis:

HDFC bank has shown its commitment towards the CSR spending. The table shows that most of the years HDFC bank has spent more than the statutory requirement. They have spent more than the minimum requirement of two percent. The table shows that increase in profit has positively impacted on CSR and CSR spending also has increased. ICICI Bank has not made statutory compliance in first five years while last five years bank has spent as per the requirement of the companies act 2013. The bank has spent around two percent in first five years while in last five years bank has spent more than five percent. The Axis Bank's CSR expenditure has been roller-coaster. Although the percentage wise bank has made statutory compliance in all the years except one year i.e. 2016-17 where bank spent 1.85 percentages. CSR has been fluctuating maybe because of fluctuation in profit. It means banks profit is affecting the CSR spendings. It simply means higher the profit higher the CSR spending. IDBI bank has not made statutory compliance in any year. Bank has faced financial crises for a longer period; the bank could make enough profit which can be spent on CSR. Bank could manage to spend on CSR in four years out of ten years. The first-year bank could spend more than one percent while in second year bank has spent below the one percentage. The last two years bank has managed to spend more than one percent but below the two percent which is statutory requirement. The table IndusInd indicates that bank has bank has not made statutory compliance in first five years while in second half bank has spent more than two

percent. In the second half, although the percentage of CSR spending has been increasing, the actual amount spent has not increased significantly. Still bank has managed to show upward trend in graph as the profit increased bank has increased its expenditure.

Findings:

1. Public sector banks have not spent more than one percent in their whole period of ten years. SBI has managed to spend more than two percent but that is in one year only.
2. Among the all public sector banks, SBI is the only bank which has continuously spent on CSR. The bank has shown consistency in their CSR spending. The other banks have not spent satisfactorily on CSR.
3. All public sector banks have done their CSR activities as a voluntary and not a mandatory activity.
4. Most of the private sector banks have tried to make statutory compliance of the CSR spending.
5. Some private sector banks have partially made statutory compliance of spending CSR while some has fallen short.
6. HDFC bank has been leading in CSR spending while other banks have shown their commitment towards the CSR but fallen short in making statutory compliance.

Suggestions:

1. All public sector banks need to follow the companies' act 2013 for spending CSR.
2. Since the functioning of the private banks and public banks are the same, there is no need to give exemptions to public sector banks in spending CSR.
3. Private Banks need to be more serious and committed towards the making statutory compliance of CSR spending.
4. Since there is a direct connection of profitability and CSR, banks should focus on making more profit so that they can spent on CSR every year.
5. CSR has a potential to change the face of the society. Banking companies can play crucial role in reaching to the bottom level citizen. Therefore, all the banks should spend good amount of funds on CSR activities. RBI and government should motivate these banks.

Conclusion:

Banks are veins of the nation. It plays a crucial role in developing national economy. On the other hand, CSR has a potential which can change the current situation of the society. When banking companies do the CSR in well-structured form and systematic implementation of it will help nation to achieve goal of sustainable development. It will reduce the burden of the government where they needed to spend more on social welfare. There are sectors like education, healthcare, rural development where bank can spend systematically which can solve the major problem of the society at large.

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